

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO DEVELOP CREATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: in this thesis, effective ways to develop creativity aspects in requirements, ideas about creating new ideas in educational and independent work processes in order to acquire creative qualities are highlighted.

Key words: qualities of creativity, knowledge, skills, competence, creative activity, personal creativity, professional creativity.

In order for students studying in the higher education system to have creative qualities, they need to think about new ideas different from the traditional approach, originality, and initiative in the processes of learning and independent work. Therefore, a future pedagogue with creative qualities should take a creative approach in organizing his professional activities, be active in creating new, advanced, ideas that serve to develop students' educational activities and personal qualities, independently use advanced pedagogical achievements and experiences. learning also focuses on having the experience of continuous, consistent exchange of ideas with colleagues about pedagogical advances.

Usually, the ability of pedagogues to be creative is ensured by striving to solve pedagogical problems, carrying out scientific research or scientific projects, and achieving mutual creative cooperation. A teacher does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed over a period of time through consistent study and work, and it gradually improves and develops.

In order for future music teachers to have creativity, as in any specialist, the foundation is laid in their student years and it is consistently developed in the organization of professional activity. It is important for the student to direct himself to creative activity and be able to organize this activity effectively. In the organization of creative activity, the student should pay special attention to solving problematic issues, analyzing problematic situations, as well as creating creative products of a pedagogical nature. While solving problematic issues and situations, his creative approach to independently finding a solution to the problem helps him develop emotional and willful qualities. By putting problematic issues in front of him, the student is faced with evidence that contradicts his existing knowledge and life experiences. As a result, he feels the

need to work on himself, study independently. Music-pedagogical activities and the implementation of scientific or creative projects of the future music teacher will further develop the potential of creativity. A student's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activities.

As mentioned, creativity qualities do not develop spontaneously in future music teachers, as in all individuals. Accordingly, there are a number of ways to successfully develop the qualities of creativity.

The first way is to develop creative thinking skills. In this, the main emphasis is on the formation of creative thinking skills, and students are directed to express the essence of creative actions with the help of verbs. In particular, teachers pay attention to the presence of necessary verbs in questions that encourage students to think in order to effectively form creative thinking skills. If this situation is explained with examples, the control question asking students to "describe the relationship between major and minor sounds" does not form creativity in them. After all, the concept of "describe" in the question is equivalent to saying "tell your existing knowledge one by one".

When asking control questions, using words (verbs) that encourage students to think makes it easier for them to think creatively. Therefore, according to the first way of forming creative qualities in a person, it is appropriate for pedagogues to use words (verbs) that force to give different, antique, unconventional and thorough answers. For example, the use of words (verbs) such as "find a connection", "create", "predict", "explain an idea logically", "imagine" is considered effective from a practical point of view.

If, instead of asking students to "describe the relationship between major and minor sounds", the teacher should ask them to "give all kinds of relationships between the system of major and minor sounds". , as a result, students will have the opportunity to generalize existing knowledge and to put forward new thoughts and ideas.

It is advisable for pedagogues to use the first way - to use the "Creativity Map" of young teachers in the formation of creativity skills in students.

The second way is to develop practical creative thinking skills. Educators use instructional methods and methods to form and develop creative thinking skills in students. In this case, the use of questions can help only in the short term, it does not develop interactivity and initiative in students.

The third way is the organization of creative processes. In this way, emphasis is placed on creative thinking of students in the process of solving

problems and promoting innovative ideas. Although creative methods and methods are not actively used in these processes, creative thinking occurs. For example, while completing the task of "finding the relationship between the system of major and minor sounds", students will analyze various problems related to the human circulatory system. As a result, multi-faceted thinking and observation takes place in this process.

The fourth way is to use creative products (developments). In this way, the pedagogue can give the students the task of creating a presentation on the topic of "system of major and minor sounds" using Power Point software or multimedia tools. In the process of preparing the presentation, students actively develop creative thinking skills. Students can fully demonstrate their creative thinking skills in a comfortable environment.

If students have a feeling of fear of failure, if they hesitate to express their opinion incorrectly, if they are afraid of criticism, in such a situation it will not be possible to effectively form or develop their creative thinking skills. The ability to think creatively can be successfully formed only by making creativity a habit in students. In this process, the methods and tools used by them in the assessment of their thorough understanding of the content of the subject and creative thinking skills are of great importance.

As a result of practicing creative thinking skills, students not only rely on established connections, but also tend to establish new, meaningful connections in the brain, develop new ideas, and think in a new way. As a result of regular exercises, new creative thinking becomes habitual and automatic. The human brain is always used to working correctly, that is, there is only one correct answer for the brain. However, this is not creativity. Creativity means that all answers can be correct as students defend their views. Immersion in the atmosphere of creativity is considered. Therefore, in order to make creative thinking a habit, students should be able to look at this process with confidence.

Only if students' creativity is encouraged and a friendly environment is created, they can make creative thinking a habit. In a creative environment, teachers and students learn to treat others with sincerity and respect their opinions. Feelings such as fear of making a mistake or failure, focusing on excessive grades, being different from others, being despised and criticized, and fear of being humiliated prevent the formation of creativity in students.

Just as any skill can be developed, the ability or skill of creative thinking can also be developed. This also applies to students, and working on creativity helps

students think outside the box. However, motivating students to be creative depends on how competent the teacher is.

Researches on creativity and the works of creativity theorists serve as a guide for the formation of creativity skills in students. It "includes the environment in the auditorium, the formation of the way of thinking in students, the approach and strategic elements of the teacher." The teacher plays a special role in forming students' creative thinking skills. However, the teacher should create an environment in the audience where students can feel free and share their thoughts and ideas.

Students should express their creativity in the audience in different ways. In order to further activate the processes taking place in the minds of students, it is necessary to deviate from the established rules and standards and act freely in answering various questions. This is manifested in the student's independent work.

The teacher supports creativity in students by revealing unusual ideas and encouraging them verbally and non-verbally. The correct attitude of the teacher to the creative ideas given by the students is important for their understanding of possible and impossible conditions. All of these elements are an important part of the teacher-student relationship and ensure student success.

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